

IoT Based Smart Student Safety Tracking and Monitoring System

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Abstract:

Student's safety is one of the most important concerns of all educational institutions. Specifically the universities are assigning some committee members to monitor the movements of students in and outside colleges and universities. This project team is minimizing management work by tracking the students in and around the university and storing the records of the students. The log file will be used to analyze and process accordingly. It will automatically detect the student presence in the university. The project team is planning to use Radio-frequency identification (RFID) Reader and Card for tracking the students who are entering and leaving the university. RFID uses electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track tags attached to objects. The tags contain electronically stored information. When the student enters the main gate of the entrance, the RFID tower will read the RFID tag to be used in the ID card of the student. We will be using IOT technology with RFID technique to monitor and track the students in the university. In order to reduce the human involvement to check the student's entry and exit in and out of our university, help the university to monitor the number of students entered in the university, The University will use this data to Analyze student's presence in the university and management will decide and provide good services and support based on the report. This system will connect to cloud based application to send notification to parents. This system will ensure the safety of students in the university.

Keywords: IoT, Security, RFID, Technology and System